

Assisted Flight Control for Aerial Contact UAVs in Industrial Environments.

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Abstract—This paper describes the state machine of an autonomous contact UAV for assisted inspection tasks. The UAV is able to control its position using on-board sensors, while the human operator sends the high-level directives. The internal controller of the robot is aware of the state machine status, granting that the control signals that reach the autopilot are smooth, when transitioning between the different control modes. The article summarizes the control modes associated to state machine’s states, describes the rules for the smooth transitions, and shows experimental results. Indoor experiments are evaluated with a VICON system, and outdoors experiments show a qualitative representation of those smooth shifts between the states.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in industrial facilities is starting to become a reality. Their ability to reach locations of difficult access has unprecedented benefits to this market. Currently, most of the inspection and maintenance tasks in industrial facilities are performed by specialized human operators working at height. The use of ropes and scaffolds is the daily inspection routine. However, it is widely known that many labor accidents occur due to their use. Additionally, the setup of these infrastructures for the inspection requires time and cost. The use of UAVs to replace the need of ropes and scaffolds will utterly benefit the inspection services in terms of time and profit.

Contact aerial robotics is a particular line of research that focuses on enabling robots to interact physically with the environment. This ability will enable brand-new robots for a large variety of operations. The number of research publications in this field has increased exponentially in the latest years.

Contact drones range from Aerial Manipulators such as [1], [2], [3], *pushing* drones as [4] or sensor placement [5].

One of the application fields is Inspection and Maintenance (I&M). Authors in [4], [6], [7] show different approaches for simple contact UAVs designed to push an NDT sensor on surfaces for thickness evaluation or defects detection. Authors in [8] added an articulated manipulator to be able to select more accurately where to place the sensor, but this design was strictly restricted to ceilings and the

work-space of the manipulator is limited. Ikeda et al. [9] designed an UAV with a 1DoF moving part to orientate the pitch of the sensor. But all of these designs lack of the same skill: to move along the surface without detaching.

To overcome this issue, our platform has an embedded wheeled crawler at the tip of the end-effector, which allows our platform to freely move over the surface without requiring it to fly back-and-forth. This research extends the work presented in [10].

This paper shows a state machine aware control architecture which focuses on granting smooth transitions between the different controllers. Each state owns different controller parameters and estimators. Consequently, our UAV is able to change from a non-contact to contact, transitioning safely. Besides, the different control modes will be introduced, showing experimental results of their performance both in the *Lab* and on the *Field*.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The system has been designed to have autonomy in the tracking of the inspection commands. This means that it follows the references provided by the inspector on ground autonomously. With this purpose, the robot is provided with the necessary equipment to autonomously control its position given an estimator. In this work, three sources of estimation are used. The first one is what we called the contact position estimator. The second one is the assisted flight position estimator. And the third one is the approach flight position estimator.

Fig. 1. Main coordinate systems of the aerial platform. From left to right the coordinate systems belong to: T265 camera, Aerox autopilot, D435 camera and crawler

Figure 1 shows the four main coordinate of the systems. The center one is the coordinate system of the autopilot, any control signal will end up transformed to it in order to command the platform. Then, there is the coordinate system of the crawler, which represents the contact point and will be

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used to generate a relative position estimation to control the robot while flying in contact. There is the coordinate system of the visual sensor, which will be used as reference for the estimation of the position of the aerial robot when it is in free flight before the contact state. And the last coordinate system corresponds to the frontal distance sensor used to obtain a relative estimation of the position of the drone when transitioning from flying to contact.

A. State machine based controller

From the take-off to the contact, the drone transits through 3 stages: *assisted*, *approaching* and *contact*. Each of these stages require different position estimators and the dynamics might change, so the control have different parameters.

Fig. 2. Available states of the controller.

Figure 2 shows the states and allowed transitions in the state machine. In the implementation described in this paper, each of the states has a PID-controller, which parameters have been tuned according to the different position estimators. Additionally, to make the system safer, each node has different safety conditions that can force the state machine to transit to a safer control-mode.

B. Transitions between states

For the transitions between the states, it is important to keep the continuity between the control signals to prevent abrupt movements. Each parameter of the each PID vary, thus the internal states should adjust accordingly too. These are the rules used to adjust PID parameters in the transitions:

- The derivative term is inhibit in the first iteration at the new state to prevent a large peak due to the changes in references and estimations.
- The accumulated error is scaled according to the factor $\frac{k'_i}{k_i}$. This is very important in the presence of persistent forces such as in the vertical axis (lift, thrust value) and in the presence of persistent wind.

As observed in Figure 3, by applying these two conditions, we prevent abrupt changes in the integral and derivative terms in the PID controller when transitioning from one controller to the next one.

C. Assisted Controller

This is the simplest state, the controller relies on the estimation of an Intel RealSense T265 [11] as estimate for the controller. The camera is located on the right side of the drone, so a transform is needed to move to the coordinate frame of the autopilot. To perform the movement, a pilot will

Fig. 3. Example of transition between PID controllers.

change the reference along the axis of the UAV. This means that the control being executed tries to follow a reference set by the pilot in XYZ axis, instead of following the roll, pitch, yaw and thrust, which is the standard mode flight.

D. Approaching Controller

This state uses two different sensors for the position estimation of the drone: a depth sensing device, placed in the manipulator to obtain a dense point cloud of the surface in front of the platform and the Intel RealSense T265 [11] mentioned above. The idea is to control the movement of the UAV in the orientation of the manipulator, to allow the platform to reach the contact state safely. In this way, the system is trying to position itself perpendicularly to the surface, enabling an easier approaching.

The operator chooses from a set of possible surfaces, such as a plane, sphere or cylinder, accordingly to the structure to be inspected. With that hint, the algorithm performs RANSAC [12] to estimate the surface to be contacted. Meanwhile, the movements perpendicular to the surface of the UAV are controlled with the same estimates as in the assisted flight.

Fig. 4. Example of approach state operation.

In Figure 4, a diagram of how the approach state operates can be observed. In this case, an interpolation of the plane is calculated from the curved surface, to estimate a normal, which will determine the *yaw* of the UAV. As a result, if the platform moves laterally, the platform will rotate to maintain the manipulator perpendicular to the surface.

Both estimators could be replaced, if desired, with other position estimators, such as a LiDAR or a front camera with some tracking algorithm to target a specific spot. Nevertheless, changing them will not affect in any sense the rest of the system.

E. Contact Controller

This state uses a different position estimator. Instead of using visual sensors, it relies on the forward kinematics of the manipulator, using the sensors of the joints, to compute the position of the UAV relatively to the contact point. An example of contact can be seen in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Example of coordinate systems in a contact operation.

As described above, the wheeled crawler should be in contact with the surface in this stage, thus we can estimate the orientation of the surface and the reference position for the UAV.

The coordinates system of the crawler is in a rigid contact with the surface. But, if for some perturbation, this assumption is no longer true, the UAV needs to react and switch to the previous safe state controller. To do so, the system is continuously tracking the pushing force and also the angles at the tip of the end-effector. If any of them exceeds the safety bound, the controller switches to a safe state, in order to restart the operation.

III. SYSTEM EVALUATION

A. Lab evaluation

In these experiments the estimations used by the controller are compared against the measures of a VICON system. At first instance, the visual tracking camera T265 is evaluated. A trajectory estimation during a flight is shown in Figures 6 and 7.

In these figures, it can be observed that the estimation from the camera has drifted due to accumulated errors while mapping. However, the system is intended to be used under the commands of the inspector which closes the loop giving

Fig. 6. Sample experiment with T265 vs VICON positioning. Top image shows the trajectories from a top view. Bottom image shows the side view. T265 trajectory is shifted due to the accumulated errors in the estimator.

Fig. 7. 3D trajectory of the drone captured by the T265 device and a VICON system as *ground-truth*. The different stages are pointed out.

the motion commands. Thus, it is not critical having a lack of a fixed global reference, as the pilot will be the one modifying the reference to ensure that the UAV is positioned where desired.

In this example, the UAV took off, moved towards the surface to be inspected in *Assisted mode*. Then, before entering into contact mode, the robot switches to *Approach mode* in which the front camera is used to track the orientation of the surface and the distance to it. At this point, we commanded it to move left and right, to show how the system behaves according to this operating mode. Then it transitioned to contact and moved along the surface.

In order to evaluate the "contact" position estimator, the pose of the crawler has been tracked too. The difference between the coordinates of the crawler and the coordinates of the autopilot correspond to the contact position estimator. Figure 8 shows a comparison between the internal estimator of the manipulator and the *difference* of the two poses captured by the VICON system. The average difference between both is 2cms . This error might be caused by the difference in the real mechanical centers and the VICON centers of coordinates.

Fig. 8. Manipulator estimator against the *ground truth* calculated with the pose of the VICON.

B. Field evaluation

On field tests, it is not possible to obtain a *ground truth* as in the lab. Thus, in this section we will present the outputs of the control system outdoors as a qualitative result. Figure 9 shows the estimates and the data of the controllers (reference and control signal).

Fig. 9. Control signals during outdoor experiment.

Figure 9 shows the internal variables of the controller (estimate, reference and control signal) during the three main stages. As can be observed, there is not any noticeable abrupt control signal, thanks to the state machine aware controller transitions. As the UAV is a coplanar multirotor, it is necessary to maintain a pitch to actively exert a pushing force in the direction of the surface to remain in contact. This can be observed in the *shift* in the control signal in the X controller.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we want to illustrate the capability of our platform of performing smooth transitions between different controllers, which have different estimators. We have presented a state machine which enables an autonomous approaching state which helps the operator when setting the crawler on the surface to be inspected.

Our experimental results in the lab show consistency between our estimators and the *ground truth* obtained with the VICON technology. Furthermore, the field results exemplify how our controllers smoothly transition between each other.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Xiangdong Meng, Yuqing He, and Jianda Han. Survey on aerial manipulator: System, modeling, and control. *Robotica*, 38(7):1288–1317, 2020.
- [2] Pablo Ramon-Soria, Begoña C. Arrue, and Anibal Ollero. Grasp planning and visual servoing for an outdoors aerial dual manipulator. *Engineering*, 6(1):77–88, 2020.
- [3] Anibal Ollero, Marco Tognon, Alejandro Suarez, Dongjun Lee, and Antonio Franchi. Past, present, and future of aerial robotic manipulators. *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, pages 1–20, 2021.
- [4] Antonio E. Jimenez-Cano, Pedro J. Sanchez-Cuevas, Pedro Grau, Anibal Ollero, and Guillermo Heredia. Contact-based bridge inspection multirotors: Design, modeling, and control considering the ceiling effect. *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 4(4):3561–3568, Oct 2019.
- [5] Salua Hamaza, Ioannis Georgilas, Guillermo Heredia, Anibal Ollero, and Thomas Richardson. Design, modeling, and control of an aerial manipulator for placement and retrieval of sensors in the environment. *Journal of Field Robotics*, 37(7):1224–1245, 2020.
- [6] Basaran Bahadir Kocer, Tegoeh Tjahjowidodo, Mahardhika Pratama, and Gerald Gim Lee Seet. Inspection-while-flying: An autonomous contact-based nondestructive test using uav-tools. *Automation in Construction*, 106:102895, 2019.
- [7] L.M. González-deSantos, J. Martínez-Sánchez, H. González-Jorge, F. Navarro-Medina, and P. Arias. Uav payload with collision mitigation for contact inspection. *Automation in Construction*, 115:103200, 2020.
- [8] Pedro J. Sanchez-Cuevas, Antonio Gonzalez-Morgado, Nicolas Cortes, Diego B. Gayango, Antonio E. Jimenez-Cano, Anibal Ollero, and Guillermo Heredia. Fully-actuated aerial manipulator for infrastructure contact inspection: Design, modeling, localization, and control. *Sensors*, 20(17), 2020.
- [9] Takahiro Ikeda, Shogo Yasui, Motoharu Fujihara, Kenichi Ohara, Satoshi Ashizawa, Akihiko Ichikawa, Akihisa Okino, Takeo Oomichi, and Toshio Fukuda. Wall contact by octo-rotor uav with one dof manipulator for bridge inspection. In *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pages 5122–5127, Sep. 2017.
- [10] Anibal Ollero, Guillermo Heredia, Antonio Franchi, Gianluca Antonelli, Konstantin Kondak, Alberto Sanfeliu, Antidio Viguria, J. Ramiro Martinez-de Dios, Francesco Pierri, Juan Cortes, Angel Santamaria-Navarro, Miguel Angel Trujillo Soto, Ribin Balachandran, Juan Andrade-Cetto, and Angel Rodriguez. The aeroarms project: Aerial robots with advanced manipulation capabilities for inspection and maintenance. *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine*, 25(4):12–23, 2018.
- [11] Intel® RealSense™ Depth and Tracking Cameras. Tracking camera T265, <https://www.intelrealsense.com/tracking-camera-t265/>, 2021.
- [12] Martin A. Fischler and Robert C. Bolles. Random sample consensus: A paradigm for model fitting with applications to image analysis and automated cartography. *Commun. ACM*, 24(6):381–395, June 1981.